

KIT Royal
Tropical
Institute

RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

Contact: Rob Kuijpers
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To: Sandra Alba
By E-mail: s.alba@kit.nl
Cc: M.Straetemans@kit.nl

Amsterdam, 2 June 2022

Subject Decision Research Ethics Committee S-181

Dear Sandra Alba,

The Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the Royal Tropical Institute has reviewed your application for ethical clearance for a study titled "Research integrity and research fairness survey" (S-181) that was originally submitted on April 7, 2022, and resubmitted on April 26, 2022.

The Committee has reviewed the adapted protocol and has taken note of your amendments and clarifications and is pleased to see that you have addressed our concerns and questions to our satisfaction.

The Committee is of the opinion that the proposal meets the required ethical standards for research and herewith grants you ethical approval to implement the study as planned in the aforementioned protocol. This approval is granted considering that you will inform the GDPR project officer about your research project for GDPR monitoring purposes.

The Committee requests you to inform the Committee when substantive changes to the protocol are made, important changes to the research team take place or researchers are added to the research team.

Moreover, the Committee requests you to send the final report of the research containing a summary of the study's findings and conclusions to the Committee, for monitoring purposes by the REC.

Wishing you success with the implementation of the research,

Dr Rob Kuijpers

Chair
KIT Research Ethics Committee

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